

Prevalence of Post-Partum Haemorrhage in Jharkhand PopulationRameshwari Beck¹, Shashi Dinkar Minj², Jyoti Hosamani³¹Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics and gynaecology, Sheikh Bhikhari Medical College, Hazaribag, Jharkhand, 825301²Professor, Department of Anaesthesia, Sheikh Bhikhari Medical College, Hazaribag, Jharkhand, 825301³Senior resident, Department of Obstetrics and gynaecology, Sheikh Bhikhari Medical College, Hazaribag, Jharkhand, 825301

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Abstract:**Background:** Postpartum haemorrhage (PPH) is one of the major causes of maternal mortality and morbidity globally, especially in underdeveloped countries, including India.**Method:** Out of 700 pregnant women, 90 (ninety) women with PPH were studied. Apart from biochemical and haematological studies, IV fluid, use of oxytocin, epidosin, PV exam, episiotomy, blood transfusion, and manual removal of the placenta were also tried. Clinical manifestations were noted and treated accordingly.**Results:** Out of 90 PPH cases, 33 (36.6%) were prima gravida, 57 (63.3%) were multigravida, 57 (63.1%) were stable, 33 (36.6%) had unstable haemodynamicity status, 21 (23.3%) had vaginal delivery, 36 (40%) had caesarean delivery, 6 (6.4%) had assisted breach delivery, 12 (13.3%) had induction, 9 (10%) had prolonged delivery, and 6 (6.6%) had macrosomia.**Conclusion:** As PPH is a major cause of mortality and morbidity, early diagnosis of risk factors and etiology of PPH can prevent morbidity and mortality in such cases.**Keywords:** Morbidity and Mortality, Uterine Atony, Coagulation Failure, Hemodynamicity, Septicemia, Jharkhand.

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Introduction

Postpartum haemorrhage (PPH) remains a major cause of maternal morbidity and mortality in developing countries, including India [[1]. PPH occurs in 5% of all deliveries, the majority of deaths, occurs within four hours of delivery, indicating that it is the consequence of the third stage of labor [2]. Hysterectomy is the traditional treatment for cases of refractory PPH [3] when all methods fail to arrest bleeding. Advances in interventional radiology and the latest surgical techniques have provided safe and effective alternatives to hysterectomy in many cases of PPH [4]. Hence, an attempt is made to evaluate the hemodynamic status.

Material and Method

90 (ninety) full-term pregnant women with PPH were admitted at the Labor Room of obstetrics and gynecology department of Sheikh Bhikhari Medical College Hazaribag, Jharkhand, 825301, were studied.

Inclusive Criteria: The patients with secondary and primary PPH were included in the study. After direct visualization of the artery during laparotomy, during LSCS who had blood loss > 1500 ml but

were hemodynamically unstable were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Those patients who had a cardiac or epileptic history, and some patients who were on anti-depression therapy. HIV-positive patients were excluded from the study.

Method: A detailed history of each patient was noted, including age and socio-economic status. The obstetric history included the duration of the onset of pain and a history of vaginal leaks or bleeding. Methods of intervention like use of IV fluid, use of oxytocin, epidosin, per-vaginal examination, ARM, any inducing agent installation, episiotomy given, any instrumental use, blood transfusion, and manual removal of the placenta were tried and noted.

The duration of the study was from October 2022 to May 2024.

Statistical analysis: Parity, severity and causes of hemorrhage, pregnancy related variables, and types of labor-related perimorbital conditions were classified by percentage. The statistical analysis was carried out in SPSS software.

Observation and Results

Table 1: Study of parity cases in PPH: 33 (36.6%) were primi gravida, 57 (63.3%) were multigravida.

Table 2: Hemodynamic status in post-partum hemorrhagic patients: 57 (63%) were stable, and 33 (36.6%) had unstable status.

Table 3: Clinical manifestation in PPH patients: 9 (10%) had retained placenta, 12 (13.3%) had genital tract trauma, 40 (44.4%) had uterine atony, 13 (14.4%) had abruption, and 16 (17.7%) had coagulation failure.

Table 4: Types of labors in PPH patients: 21 (23.3%) had vaginal delivery,

36 (40%) had caesarean delivery, 6 (6.4%) had assisted breech delivery, 12 (13.3%) had induction, 9 (10%) had prolonged delivery, and 6 (6.6%) had macrosomia.

Table 5: Study of Perinatal Morbidity in PPH Patients: 21 (23.3%) NICU admissions, 33 (36.6%) were prematurity of fetus, 15 (16%) had jaundice, 12 (13.3%) had septicemia, and 9 (10%) were normal (no morbidity).

Table 1: Study of parity cases in PPH (No of patients: 90)

Sl. No	Details of Parity	No. of Cases	Percentage %
1	Primi gravida	33	36.6
2	Multi gravida	57	63.3

Figure 1: Study of parity cases in PPH

Table 2: Hemodynamic status in post-partum haemorrhage (PPH) patients (No of patients: 90)

Sl. No	Details of Hemodynamicity	No. of case	Percentage
1	Stable	57	63.1
2	Un-stable	33	36.6

Figure 2: Hemodynamic status in post-partum haemorrhage (PPH) patients

Table 3: Clinical Manifestations of post-partum Haemorrhage (PPH)

Sl. No	Particulars	No. of cases	Percentage
1	Retained placenta	9	10
2	Genital tract trauma	12	13.3
3	Uterine atony	40	44.4
4	Abruption	13	14.4
5	Coagulation failure	16	17.7

Figure 3: Clinical Manifestations of post-partum Haemorrhage (PPH)

Table 4: Types of labours in PPH patients (No of patients: 90)

Sl. No	Types of labours	No of cases	Percentage
1	Vaginal Delivery	21	23.3
2	Caesarean Delivery	36	40
3	Assisted Breech Delivery	6	6.4
4	Induction	12	13.3
5	Prolonged labour	9	10
6	Macrosomia	6	6.6

Figure 4: Types of labours in PPH patients

Table 5: Study of perinatal morbidity in PPH patients (No of patients: 90)

Sl. No	Perinatal morbidity details	No. of cases	Percentage
1	NICU Admission	21	23.3
2	Prematurity	33	36.6
3	Jaundice	15	16
4	Septicaemia	12	13.3
5	Normal (No Morbidity)	9	10

Figure 5: Study of perinatal morbidity in PPH patients

Discussion

Present study of prevalence of PPH in Jharkhand population. Out of 700 full term pregnant women, 90 (ninety) had PPH. In the cases, parity 33 (36.6%) had primi gravida, and 57 (63.3%) had multi gravida (Table 1). In the study of hemodynamic status, 57 (63.1%) had stable and 33 (36.6%) had unstable hemodynamic status (Table-2). The clinical manifestations had 9 (10%) retained placenta, 12 (13.3%) had trauma to the genital tract, 40 (44.4%) had uterine atony, 13 (14.4%) had abruption, and 16 (17.7%) had coagulation failure (Table 3). The types of labor were: 21 (23.3%) had vaginal delivery, 36 (40%) had caesarean delivery, 6 (6.4%) assisted breach delivery, 12 (13.3%) had induction, 9 (10%) had prolonged labor and 6 (6.3%) had macrosomia (Table 4). In the study of perinatal morbidities, 21 (23.3%) were admitted to the NICU, 33 (36.6%) had prematurity, 15 (16%) had jaundice, 12 (13.3%) had septicemia, and 9 (10%) had normal morbidity (Table 5). These findings are more or less in agreement with previous studies [5,6,7].

The major causes of PPH are atony of the uterus, trauma, retained placenta, or abnormalities. Most of the cause is uterine atony, which is episodic and unpredictable. Women are known to have risk factors for PPH; appropriate steps for prevention should be taken during antenatal and intrapartum periods to reduce this risk. It was also reported that PPH can also occur with no risk factors [8].

The important steps in the management of PPH are predicting PPH and assessing blood loss during the

third stage of labor. The visual estimation of blood loss after delivery is inaccurate. Weighing of soaked swabs, active periodic estimation, and a written and pictorial guide to aid visual estimation in labor wards may improve the accuracy of the estimation of blood loss [9].

The protocol for the management of major PPH was: Maintain Hb% >8 gm/dl, platelet count > 75X10⁹X1, prothrombin <1.5Xmean control, prothrombin time < 1.5xmean control, fibrinogen > 1.0 gm/l, high concentration of O₂ (15l/minute), to maintain pulse rate, BP, and oxygen saturation using an oximeter. ECG, Foleys catheter to measure urinary output, fluid balance chart, blood transfusion in major PPH.

These may be one or more causes of PPH: tone, tissue, trauma, or thrombin, but the most common cause of PPH is uterine atony. If the pharmacological method fails to control bleeding in cases of atonic PPH, exclude other or additional causes by undertaking a clinical examination in the theatre, and the next intervention, the mechanical method of balloon catheter tethered, is instituted before considering a surgical procedure [10]. Moreover Radiological management for embolism of the uterine artery in atonic and traumatic PPH. Hysterectomy was avoided in major PPH by arterial embolism to maintain fertility [11]. Surgical procedures include uterine compression sutures, vascular ligations, and post-partum hysterectomy. Recombinant activated factor VII and the role of tranexamic acid also played a significant role in controlling PPH.

Summary and Conclusion

The present study of PPH in the Jharkhand population will be quite useful for obstetricians and gynecologists, physicians, radiologists, and pathologists to treat PPH efficiently to prevent high-risk factors and active management labor. It requires a multidisciplinary approach, which is essential in severe hemorrhage.

The availability of blood and blood products is very essential. It is a matter of thought that in some patients, PPH can also occur with no risk factors. This study demands further hematological (angiological), genetic, nutritional, histopathological, and hormonal studies because the exact pathogenesis of PPH is still unclear.

Limitation of study: Owing to the tertiary location of the research centre, the small number of patients and the lack of the latest technique, we have limited findings and results.

This research study was approved by the Ethical Committee of Sheikh Bhikhari Medical College Hazaribag Jharkhand 825301.

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